

Integration of Partial Models of Multi-Agent Systems through Abstraction

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I. INTRODUCTION

Cyber Physical Systems (CPS) are inherently complex and incorporate interacting heterogeneous subsystems. Model based design of complex CPS is a multi-scope, multi-aspect challenge, which commonly means that the design and validation phase of CPS:s gives rise to a multitude of models expressed in several fundamentally different formalisms and tools. Achieving system-wide simulation by integrating heterogeneous and partial models is nontrivial and there is currently a lack of a rigorous methodology to perform such orchestrations.

Comprehensive model based design of smart factories and automated systems related to industry 4.0, implies compositions of dynamics, control and communication models. Such multi-agent systems that coordinate networks of individually operating Automated Guided Vehicles (AGV) represent systems with highly complex dynamics. To achieve comprehensive simulation of such multi-agent systems and enable reliable controller design, we propose partial model integration through abstracting models formulated in one formalism in order to embed them into another. The approach is demonstrated through the development of a Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) based indoor positioning system for a versatile pipe-less production plant.

II. POSITIONING SYSTEM FOR A MULTI AGENT SYSTEM

The positioning system of on indoor pipe-less production plant based on passive RFID technology is being developed. The plant utilizes differentially steered AGV:s to transport material between production stations over a flat surface. Each AGV is equipped with an active RFID reader that detects any tag within a given range. The reader induces a current in the antenna of the RFID tag and receives the identification number (ID) and a Received Signal Strength Indication (RSSI) value of the tag. The RSSI value is a measurement of the power present in the received radio signal, which in turn is interpreted as a distance to its origin.

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A. An RFID based positioning system

The positioning system comprises a known pattern of RFID tags on a flat surface. This means that the system keeps a record of all included tag ID:s and their position. As the reader on the AGV receives the ID and the RSSI value of the tags, the position of the reader can be calculated using trilateration when enough tags are within detection range [5]. Even though trilateration is based on three reference points to determine a position, 2D applications generally need merely two tags provided that the previous position and velocity of the reader are known [5]. In order to cover as much as possible of the plant production surface, tags are placed with a slight detection range overlap, see figure 2. The reader software is hence equipped with an anti-collision algorithm to sort the information from the simultaneously scanned tags [3].

B. Ambiguous RSSI values

Fig. 1. Measurements of RSSI values from a passive RFID tag.

Tag ID:s and RSSI values can be expected to be received at a chosen frequency. However, experiments show that the RSSI value is lost when the antennas of the tag and reader align due to magnetic field interference. Figure 1 plots recorded RSSI values from a tag as the reader approaches it. The RSSI value grows from 0 at the peripheral area of the detection range up to the maximum level of 7 when the reader is centered over the tag where the two magnetic fields are mutually inductive [2]. There is a complete loss of RSSI value exactly where the two antennas overlap. This causes the system to receive

ambiguous information, as the received RSSI value represents several potential positions in relation to the tag (see e.g. RSSI value 0 which implies both 3cm and 6cm in figure 1).

III. SIMULATION MODELS OF POSITIONING AND CONTROL

A. Model of RFID based trilateration

A simulation model was designed in MATLAB to evaluate the impact of the ambiguity in the received RSSI values on the output of the controller designed for the AGV:s. The simulation shows how an increased scanning frequency increases the risk of ambiguous RSSI values to be induced. Figure 2 depicts the simulation output of an RFID reader moving along a reference path over a grid of passive RFID tags placed 10cm apart with a detection range of 11cm each. The figure also depicts the trilaterated reader position as well as the range of the reader antenna. The trilateration algorithm uses the simulated signal strength of the tags within detection range to calculate the position of the reader. Figure 3 plots the simulated RSSI values picked up by the reader as well as indicates where the signal is lost due to antenna overlap.

Fig. 2. A MATLAB simulation of an RFID based positioning system. RFID tags (rectangles) are placed in a grid 10cm apart with a detection range (blue) of 11cm. A reader reference position (black dot) and its range (magenta) are plotted as well as the trilaterated position (red line).

Fig. 3. Simulated RSSI values received by the reader moving over an RFID covered surface. During this scenario (as illustrated in figure 2) the antennas of the reader and the tag align once and is indicated as a signal loss (red).

B. System-wide simulation model

A Nonlinear Model Predictive Controller (NMPC) has been developed by Subramanian et al [4] for the pipe-less production plant. NMPC is an optimal control technique that

determines the AGV motion while satisfying a given set of constraints. The controller was translated together with models of the AGV kinetics and system network properties into a system-wide PTOLEMY [1] model by Vercoulen [6]. However, the PTOLEMY model assumes visual feedback from an overhead camera, which will be replaced by RFID. In order to simulate the impact of changing the positioning system on the overall behavior of the multi-agent system, the PTOLEMY model should be extended.

IV. INTEGRATION OF PARTIAL MODELS

Ambiguous position feedback may have a negative impact on the controller designed for the production plant if errors are large or too frequent. Integration of the MATLAB model into the PTOLEMY model enables evaluation of the impact of the lost RSSI values on the overall system performance, while at the same time also enabling re-use of the existent PTOLEMY model. Each RSSI reading scenario of interest is recorded from the MATLAB model and abstracted into a state machine where each of the seven RSSI values is represented as a separate state for each RFID tag. The state machine is then formulated in the syntax of the system-wide PTOLEMY model to extend the positioning system component with the information errors detected in experiments. The MATLAB model abstraction captures the ambiguity of the measured position information and the partial model integration enables re-use of an already existing system-wide model as a means to achieve system performance analysis.

V. CONCLUSION

The paper presents an approach to comprehensive modeling of complex systems by embedding abstractions of component models into system-wide models expressed in other formalisms. The development of an RFID based positioning system for indoor applications is presented. A MATLAB based model of the RFID positioning system is abstracted into a state machine that represents the simulated position errors and is expressed in the syntax of a system-wide PTOLEMY model. The goal of the composition of the positioning system and the controller models of the setup is to evaluate the impact of ambiguous position information on system performance and to enable re-use of existent system-wide models to do so.

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